

Implementation of the Inaportnet Policy for Ship and Goods Services at the Office of the Main Port Authority Tanjung Perak Surabaya

Eka Prastyo M.¹, Moeheriono², Sulistyanto³

^{1,2,3} Master of Public Administration, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences Hang Tuah University, Surabaya, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: To improve services for ships and goods at ports, the Indonesian government issued various regulations to make it more efficient and attract investment so that economic activity continues to increase. One of the regulations is the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015 concerning Inaportnet. Inaportnet is an open and neutral electronic portal to facilitate the exchange of port service data and information quickly, safely, neutrally and easily. Inaportnet is integrated with relevant government agencies, port business entities, and logistics industry players to increase the competitiveness of the Indonesian logistics community.

This qualitative research method uses an implementation model according to Van Horn Van Meter. In general, the implementation of Inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority (KOP) has been going quite well, but several things need improvement to improve time efficiency and improve performance. This is relevant to aspects of policy standards and objectives/policy measures and objectives; resource; the characteristics of the implementing organization; attitude of the implementers; communication between related organizations and implementation activities; and the social, economic, socio-political environment.

Factors that support the implementation of Inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main KOP is the readiness of supporting resources, both human resources and facilities at Tanjung Perak Port Surabaya. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factor for the implementation of this policy is the technical problem of the inaportnet system. Although the implementation of the inaportnet policy has been good, there are still several things that need to be improved and improved, including operational technical aspects, legal and institutional aspects.

KEYWORDS: Implementation, Inaportnet, Policy, service, ship.

INTRODUCTION

Along with the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), especially the internet, which is rapidly changing the organizational paradigm, influencing, and even changing the business activities of an organization. Utilization of the internet as a medium in conducting business activities is believed not only to provide strategic benefits, but also to increase efficiency in its operations (Cronin, 2003). In fact, it is said that the adoption of the internet in organizations is a new method of providing services at all levels, namely society, business, and government with the aim of providing better and transparent services to the community (Nguyen, 2014).

Initially, organizations providing internet-based services had to compete with traditional organizations in providing services at low prices. However, as more organizations adopt the internet for their business services, the price factor is no longer dominant (Hongxiu & Reima, 2008). Organizations are required to provide the best service to attract customers. Therefore, issues related to service quality are important, especially the quality of internet-based services (e-service quality).

The Ministry of Transportation (Kemenhub) continues to strive to improve port performance in Indonesia. These efforts include infrastructure improvements to innovations that continue to be developed. Acting Director General of Sea Transportation, Arif Toha, said that one of the efforts to improve port performance is on the soft infrastructure side by implementing Inaportnet. Inaportnet is an internet-based electronic service information system that is centralized and collaborates with port operational service standards to serve ship and goods activities at the port. "This system has been implemented since 2016 and with Inaportnet it is hoped that there will be an increase in ship and goods services at the port so that they can run faster, validly, transparently and standardized," said Arif in a written statement, Friday (12/11/2021) (www.money.com). [.kompas.com](http://www.kompas.com))

According to Arif, the Inaportnet system can facilitate the flow of goods at the port because it makes port services more effective by providing ship and goods services 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. In addition, Inaportnet is also supported by the Ministry of Transportation's Internal system and the existing system of the Port Business Entity (BUP). "Inaportnet as a form of port digitization is also expected to reduce logistics costs by cutting operational costs so as to create optimal costs," said Arif. Arif explained that Inaportnet's services include digitizing ship arrival approvals, port entry ship approvals, loading and unloading work plans approval, as well as approval of loading and unloading of dangerous goods, determining ship services. In addition, it also includes digitizing the approval letter for ship movement, approval of the crew list, ship departure reports, ship arrival reports, ship arrival and departure reports, as well as shipping company freight reports and others.

Through the integrated Inaportnet system and QR Code, users can independently print the approval letters and the validity of the results of ship and goods services at the port. "Thus, the entire service process at the port becomes more integrated and transparent so that its validity can be trusted," said Arif. According to Arif, in implementing Inaportnet, the Port Authority and Harbormaster Office (KSOP) and the Port Operator Unit (UPP) are required to provide assistance to service users. In addition, you must always evaluate the services of ships and goods using Inaportnet on a regular basis. Then the results of the evaluation are submitted to the Directorate of Traffic and Sea Transportation of the Ministry of Transportation to be used as material for improvement and application development, as well as business process improvements and regulatory improvements.

"Inaportnet is very much needed to encourage service improvement and better port competitiveness and become the main gateway in the National Logistics Ecosystem (NLE)," said Arif. To date, Inaportnet has been utilized in 54 ports, consisting of Belawan, Tanjung Priok, Tanjung Perak, Makassar, Tanjung Emas, Dumai, Pekanbaru, Teluk Bayur, Jambi, Baai Island, Palembang, Panjang, Banten, Tanjung Pinang, Pontianak, Tanjung Pandan, Cirebon, Cilacap, Bena, Banjarmasin, Gresik, Tanjung Balai Karimun, Kotabaru/Batulicin, Balikpapan, and Samarinda. Then applied to the ports of Bontang, Kendari, Bitung, Ternate, Ambon, Sorong, Jayapura, Pangkal Balam, Tanjung Buton, Patimban, Palu Bay, Kuala Tanjung, Kijang, Tanjung Wangi, Sunda Kelapa, Sheet, Kupang, Sampit, Tarakan, Manado, Pare-Pare, Gorontalo, Biak, Bau-Bau, Thousand Islands, Marunda, Muara Angke, Satui, and Batam.

Inaportnet has a positive effect on Waiting Time for Pilot and Waiting Time for Berth. This means that the more service users use the Inaportnet system, the higher the probability of achieving Waiting Time for Pilot and Waiting Time for Berth (Wulyo, 2019). Although many have felt comfortable with the Inaportnet system, there are still some things that need improvement or improvement in order to increase the satisfaction of port service users, including anchoring, piloting, delaying, and mooring services (PPKB-D), Unloading Order List (DUB) services.), plan for loading and issuing Export Stack Cards (KSE), processing of Export Approval (PE) documents, and quarantine permits (Malisan, 2019). Ship agency services have changed the completion of ship documents from a manual system to an online system. The online system is expected to improve fast, reliable, transparent and standardized ship services so as to minimize ship handling costs at ports and be able to improve handling performance on trade activities and goods traffic, especially encouraging the acceleration of the port clearance process so that ships do not experience delays (Widayoko, 2010). 2012).

Completion of ship documents using the online system still has administrative errors that must be resolved, such as the Inaportnet system which still requires additional applications so there needs to be a commitment between related agencies and shipping companies. Changes in document settlement procedures using an online system where there should be no face-to-face contact between the service user and the licensing party actually have an impact on the slowness of licensing granted (Saifudin, 2009). The process of completing ship clearance has changed using the online system or using the Inaportnet system, but this system is still constrained by an inadequate internet connection. The number of ship documents that must be completed, the ship certificate expiration date checking system is still manual, the occurrence of ups and downs, and the length of waiting for the cargo to arrive at the port also causes the clearance process at Tanjung Perak Port to be long (Andromeda, 2020).

Clearance in ship is a ship licensing process carried out by shipping company agencies at each relevant Port agency where the ship will enter the port water area, then the area in the port until the ship docks at the dock to carry out loading and unloading activities and other activities. Clearance out of the ship is a ship departure permit process carried out by the shipping company agency at each relevant agency at the port where the ship has completed loading and unloading activities and other activities which will then leave the port to the next destination port.

The implementation of Inaportnet at the Tanjung Perak port is considered to have been able to improve ship services well. In fact, the existence of this online system can avoid physical contact between officers, both from service users and service providers. According to the Directorate General of Sea Relations, Inaportnet's go live activity in Tanjung Perak is a follow-up to the signing of the Inaportnet system integrity pact that works well if the application and its support system are well integrated, then the entire system must be built and developed synergistically, involving all stakeholders. This readiness has been carried out by the Tanjung Perak Port management by preparing all the facilities and infrastructure owned. The information needed is related to the management of sea and port traffic, for the Inaportnet application which is currently being developed by the Ministry of Transportation. To perform data and information processing, information technology facilities are used. The process starts from processing data owned by the Port Authority and Pelindo. The information carried out by data processing is related to the business processes of the Port Authority/Office of Harbor Masters and P.T. Pelindo, Shipping Company/Ship Agency, among others are as follows: (i) harbormaster who is responsible for ship departure and seaworthiness of shipping; (ii) the Navigation District which is responsible for shipping navigation and shipping safety; (iii) Pelindo which is responsible for loading and unloading activities at the port; (iv) Shipping Companies/Ship Agencies are responsible for: ensuring the smooth operation of ships at the Port, completing financial obligations (disbursement), submitting reports on the realization of ship visits at Indonesian ports. Based on the description above, this research takes the title "Implementation of Inaportnet Policy for Ships and Goods Services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office".

RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, the researcher uses qualitative research, namely research that is used to examine the condition of natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument (Sugiyono, 2017). Qualitative research is one of the research procedures that produces descriptive data in the form of speech or writing and the behavior of the people being observed. This qualitative research is expected to be able to provide a detailed explanation of phenomena that are difficult to convey using qualitative methods. while the descriptive approach is research that seeks to describe the solutions to existing problems based on data (Narbuko, 2007). Descriptive research aims to make a systematic, factual and accurate description, picture or painting of the facts, the nature of the relationship between the phenomena being investigated.

Data analysis in qualitative research is carried out during data collection, and after completing data collection within a certain period. The activities contained in it are: 1. Data Collection. Data collection is data collected in the form of words and not in the form of a series of words. The process of collecting data is done through interviews, observation, and documentation. 2. Data Condensation, Data condensation looks at the process of selecting, managing, simplifying, and or changing data that approximates the whole part of written field notes, interview texts, and other empirical material. 3. Presentation of Data (Data Display), Presentation of data in this study will be arranged clearly and in detail briefly and thoroughly so that it is easier to understand the description of the aspects studied, both in whole and in part. 4. Conclusion Drawing/Verification The final step in the interactive model qualitative data analysis is drawing conclusions from verification. Based on the data that has been reduced and presented, the researcher makes conclusions that are supported by strong evidence at the data collection stage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the authors use the Van Horn Van Meter policy implementation model where there are six aspects that are interrelated and mutually influence the success of policy implementation. the six aspects are (1) standard and policy objectives; (2) Resources; (3) Communication between Organizations and strengthening activities; (4) Characteristics of implementing agents; (5) The economic, social and political environment; (6) The attitude of the implementers.

Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the port of Tanjung Perak is applied to regulate. The implementation of Inaportnet services for ships and goods at the port is carried out according to the duties, functions, authorities and responsibilities of each government agency and relevant stakeholders at the port based on the provisions of the legislation. Government agencies and relevant stakeholders at ports include; Main Authority Office, Main Harbormaster Office, Harbormaster Office and Port Authority, Port Management Unit Office/Port Office, Customs Office, Port Health Office, Agricultural Quarantine Office, Fish Quarantine Office and Fish Quality Control, Immigration Office, Port Business Entity, Transportation Company National Sea at the Port and Loading and Unloading Company at the Port.

The implementation of the inaportnet at the Tanjung Perak port is considered to have been able to improve ship services well. In fact, the existence of this online system can avoid physical contact between officers, both from service users and service providers. According to the Director General of Hubla, Inaportnet's go live activity in Tanjung Perak is a follow-up to the signing of the Inaportnet system implementation integrity pact. Inaportnet will function well if the application together with its supporting system are well integrated, then the entire system must be built and developed synergistically, involving all stakeholders. This readiness has been carried out by the Tanjung Perak Port management by preparing all the facilities and infrastructure owned.

The information needed is related to the management of sea and port traffic, for the Inaportnet application which is currently being developed by the Ministry of Transportation. To perform data and information processing, information technology facilities are used. The process starts from processing data owned by the Port Authority and Pelindo. The information carried out by data processing is related to the business processes of the Port Authority/Office of Harbor Masters and P.T. Pelindo, Shipping Company/Ship Agency, among others are as follows: (i) harbormaster who is responsible for ship departure and seaworthiness of shipping; (ii) the Navigation District which is responsible for shipping navigation and shipping safety; (iii) Pelindo which is responsible for loading and unloading activities at the port; (iv) Shipping Company/Ship Agency is responsible for ensuring the smooth operation of ships at the Port, completing financial obligations (disbursement), submitting reports on the realization of ship visits at Indonesian ports. In this case, the researcher uses the Van Horn Van Meter policy implementation theory where there are six variables that are interrelated and influence the success of policy implementation.

1. Standards and Policy Objectives.

The performance of policy implementation can be measured by the level of success of the standards and policy objectives that are realistic with the socio-cultural existing at the level of implementing the policy. When the size and objectives of the policy are too ideal, it will be difficult to realize it. The basic measure of the policy refers to the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office. To integrate a standard port information system in physically serving ships and goods from all agencies and stakeholders, the Ministry of Transportation applies Inaportnet, which is an internet-based single electronic service system.

2. Sumber Daya

The implementation of Inaportnet for ship and port goods services is stipulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015 concerning the Implementation of Inaportnet for Ships and Goods Services at Ports, dated October 13, 2015. The implementation of Inaportnet is carried out by the Directorate General of Sea Transportation and comes into force on January 13, 2016 or three months from the date of promulgation. Inaportnet itself is for ship and goods services, which includes incoming ships, moving ships, outgoing ships, mooring extensions and service cancellations. The implementation of Inaportnet services for ships and goods at the port is carried out according to the duties, functions, authorities and responsibilities of each government agency and relevant stakeholders at the port based on the provisions of the legislation. Government agencies and relevant stakeholders at ports include; Main Authority Office, Main Harbormaster Office, Harbormaster Office and Port Authority, Port Management Unit Office/Port Office, Customs Office, Port Health Office, Agricultural Quarantine Office, Fish Quarantine Office and Fish Quality Control, Immigration Office, Port Business Entity, Transportation Company National Sea at the Port and Loading and Unloading Company at the Port.

Resources are an important factor for the implementation of a program or policy to be effective, where without resources, programs or activities are just paper documents. The resource component includes the number of staff, the expertise of the implementers. Therefore, the Surabaya Tanjung Perak Harbormaster must be adequate (number and expertise) because if the human resources are not adequate, the Ministerial Regulation cannot be implemented. In addition, educational institutions must receive support starting from the budget and facilities that can be used to carry out these activities. Resources are important in implementing a policy. Within Resources, there are several sub-elements including: actors or human resources, authority or orders, and supporting facilities as convenience in policy implementation.

3. Communication between Organizations

This factor emphasizes how the government socializes the policy throughout the Port Authority Office and sea transportation service companies. The role of the government here is very important in order to inform the intent and purpose of the policy so

that it can be understood and realized properly. In addition, how the socialization techniques conveyed to the implementers will result in consistency in the success of the policy.

The implementation of policy orders is transmitted to capable people and the orders made must be clear, accurate, consistent. In communication there are several sub elements including: transmission, clarity, and consistency.

3.1. Transmission

The transmission process in a policy is not only conveyed to the implementor, but must also be conveyed to the target group and other interested parties either directly or indirectly. Implementers can implement a decision when they already know what has been made and determined. The Ministry of Transportation cq the Directorate General of Sea Transportation carries out an Online Evaluation of the Implementation of Inaportnet SPS (Syahbandar Approval Letter) and the Socialization of PM.8 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Ship Service Through Inaportnet. The aim is to prepare and improve the skills of Human Resources (HR) and optimize the application of the features that are accommodated in the Inaportnet Application in each Technical Implementation Unit (UPT). PM socialization. 8 of 2022 as a form of refreshment for Inaportnet officers, service users / shipping agents, related agencies and stakeholders who are integrated with the Inaportnet System for ship and goods services. So that the officers at UPT, service users and related stakeholders are considered capable and proficient in operational services using the Inaportnet system. The implementation of Inaportnet at the Port is carried out based on the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number PM. 154 of 2015 concerning Online Harbor Master Approval (SPS) at ports and Minister of Transportation Regulation Number PM. 8 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Ship Service Through Inaportnet is a replacement for the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number PM. 192 of 2015 Amendment to the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number PM. 157 of 2015 concerning the Implementation of Inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Port which aims to improve services and the smooth flow of goods at ports, cut service time to be faster and more efficient, reduce logistics costs and as a step for service transparency at ports.

3.2. Clarity

The process of clarity that is carried out in a policy so that it is transmitted to the implementers and the target group (target group) can then be received clearly so that they can know what the intent, purpose, target of the substance of the policy are. If what is conveyed is ambiguous, they will not know what should be prepared and implemented so that policy objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently. In the context of the clarity process, setting the goals of a program is determined in advance from the basic aspects of the goals of an organization. The purpose of the program socialization is to provide information to service users to be accepted and implemented by Inaportnet service users. Based on the results of interviews from informants in the field that the flow for the application is clear, this is evidenced by the existence of guidelines/guidance in its use. And all of them can be accessed on the <https://inaportdev.dephub.go.id/site/login> page. The page contains several guidelines such as Arrival News and Departure News. The clarity of this information can be proven by the manual Book. National sea transportation companies at ports, loading and unloading companies at ports and transportation management service companies can access the website address //inaportnet.dephub.go.id, where there are 16 modules.

3.3. Consistency

The process of consistency in a policy is needed in communicating information so that the policy does not change so that it can confuse policy implementers, target groups and interested parties. Consistency contains content which can be interpreted as policy implementation will run effectively if the implementation order is consistent and clear. As a form of the Government's commitment to support the ease of sea transportation services, the Inaportnet system is used as a single internet/web-based service system that integrates a standard port information system serving ships and goods at the port from all relevant agencies or stakeholders at the port. This Inaportnet system is applied to 16 (sixteen) ports in stages. As a form of government consistency in implementation, the Government hopes that the implementation of Inaportnet will have an impact on improving ship and goods services at all ports in Indonesia so that they can run fast, validly, transparently, and standardized with minimal costs so as to increase the competitiveness of ports in Indonesia.

4. Characteristics of Implementing Agent

There is professionalism in work and adequate understanding in working in accordance with SOPs. Not only that, this factor also emphasizes the responsibility of a leader in the Surabaya Tanjung Perak Harbor who must dare to take policies and officials with an interest in regulations must play their roles with a sense of responsibility in order to achieve policy objectives.

Bureaucracy is one of the institutions that are all implementers in activities. Its existence is not only in government structures, but also in private organizations, educational institutions and others. Fundamental factors in the bureaucracy are also directly related to individual performance in reviewing the implementation of public policies that are complex and require cooperation from various parties. When the bureaucratic structure is in a state that is not conducive to policy implementation, it can lead to ineffectiveness and hinder the implementation of policies. (Agustino, 2016) suggests that there are two main characteristics of bureaucracy, namely: Making Standard Operational Procedures (SOP) and Implementing fragmentation.

The Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Harbormaster Office has implemented an Inaportnet service system (Malisan & Tresnawati, 2019) including a Sailing Approval Letter (SPB) and an Online Ship Movement Approval Letter (SPOGK) which also requires a Scout Work Order (SPK Pandu) that in order to carry out the provisions of Article 46 and Article 48 of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number: PM 57 of 2015 concerning Ship Guidance and Towage and to determine the level of service delivery and activities for the implementation of Ship Guiding and Towing in the waters of the Tanjung Perak Port of Surabaya Mandatory Scouting Waters which include safety aspects, in the context of guaranteeing the safety of sailing and anchoring in ports, the government stipulates the existence of mandatory scouting waters, every sailing ship is obliged to use scouting services. The implementation of scouting at the port is carried out by the Port Operator Unit and can be delegated to a Port Business Entity that meets the requirements. There is a fee for scouting. The pilotage fee is waived for: (a) warships; and (b) state ships used for government duties (Article 198 of Law No. 17 of 2008 concerning Shipping). Scout officers must meet the requirements for health, skills, as well as education and training as evidenced by a certificate. Scout officers are required to carry out their duties based on shipping safety and security standards.

Guidance on the ship does not reduce the authority and responsibility of the Master (Article 199 of Law No. 17 of 2008 concerning Shipping). Managers of special terminals or Port Business Entities that manage and operate pilotage, are required to pay a percentage of the income derived from scouting services to the Government as Non-Tax State Revenue (Article 200 of Law No. 17 of 2008 concerning Shipping) (Sunarto, 2015). Ship scouting services, including jobs that are required to have responsibilities in work, cooperation, initiatives and excellent physical conditions. The main thing in the implementation of pilotage operations is the smoothness, security, and safety of the guided ship because of the consequences of an negligence on the pilotage of the ship that affects the smooth traffic at the port. Service and performance in order to improve quality in the implementation of ship delaying activities as well as to realize safety and security in the waters of the Tanjung Perak Port, Surabaya, it is necessary to conduct an assessment of the personnel and auxiliary equipment on duty. Scout Assessment / Pilot Assessment and Vessel Verification As a Guiding Assistance Tool.

5. Implementing Attitude

Implementing staff is the main resource in implementing policies, staff is also commonly referred to as human resources. Resources in this case are closely related to the implementation of policies implemented to facilitate services at ports. As an effort to facilitate the implementation of the policy, the Director General of Sea Transportation asked the Directors within the Directorate General of Sea Transportation and their staff together with the Center for Information and Communication Technology for Transportation and the perpetrators of implementing the Inaportnet system to explore and appreciate and follow up the inaportnet system with joint efforts. Authority or commonly called authority is the main requirement for implementers in carrying out the established policies and authority must be formal in order to carry out orders. Formal authority can have various positive impacts on policy implementation. When that authority is misused by policies for personal or group interests, the effectiveness of the authority will be disrupted. The presence of authority becomes very important when dealing with a problem, namely conflict, from the conflict so that it can be resolved in a limited time by determining attitudes and making decisions to resolve the problem.

In carrying out a program, rights or authority are needed so that the objectives can be achieved properly. The determination of authority also makes the implementers and beneficiaries able to carry out their roles well. Regarding the implementation of inaportnet for ship and goods services at ports, it is regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015 concerning the Implementation of Inaportnet for Ships and Goods Services at the Port. So that to integrate a standard port information system in physically serving ships and goods from all agencies and stakeholders, the Ministry of Transportation implements Inaportnet, which is an internet-based single electronic service system. The implementation of Inaportnet for ship and port goods services is stipulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 157 of 2015 concerning the Implementation of Inaportnet for Ships and Goods Services at Ports, dated

October 13, 2015. Implementation of Inaportnet is carried out by the Directorate General of Sea Transportation and comes into force on January 13, 2016 or three months from the date of promulgation. Inaportnet itself is for ship and goods services, which includes incoming ships, moving ships, outgoing ships, mooring extensions and service cancellations. The implementation of Inaportnet services for ships and goods at the port is carried out according to the duties, functions, authorities and responsibilities of each government agency and relevant stakeholders at the port based on the provisions of the legislation.

6. Economic, Social and Political Environment

The economic, social and political environment at the Port of Tanjung Perak Surabaya has an influence on the implementation of the internet port policy at that location. This can be seen from several aspects, for example the existing physical facilities at the Surabaya Tanjung Perak Port. Physical facilities are an important factor in policy implementation. Physical facilities can be in the form of facilities and infrastructure. Without physical facilities, policy implementation will be hampered and will not succeed. Implementers may have sufficient ability, understand what is being done, and have authority in carrying out their duties, but if they do not have sufficient facilities such as physical facilities, program implementation will not run effectively or may even hinder it.

The government continues to improve services in a comprehensive, comprehensive and integrated manner in the export/import process, for example, import services are only based on 1 (one) import document (PIB) and submitted electronically (on-line) and with a single submission process, physical inspection imported goods are carried out immediately and the importer does not delay its implementation, selective physical inspection based on risk management for export goods subject to export duty, electronic payment management and/or deposit of state revenues, the process of monitoring (tracking) PIB/PEB documents does not require a User ID. The Service Level Standard (SLS) reference uses Inaportnet for ship and goods services at the port. SLS is measured by units of time and so on. The Inaportnet system actually provides benefits in ensuring transparency of ship and goods services at the port, fairness of service (first come first served), speeding up the completion of ship and goods services, minimizing the costs required in handling ship and goods services, increasing the validity and accuracy of data related to ship and goods service activities, and increase national competitiveness and encourage investment. Based on this, all commercial vessels at Tanjung Perak Port can be served by the Inaportnet system. However, there are some quality of services that still need improvement.

7. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of Inaportnet Policy Implementation

Factors that support the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office is the readiness of supporting resources, both human resources and facilities at Tanjung Perak Port Surabaya. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factors for the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office consist of several obstacles as follows:

- a) Under certain conditions the network connection is interrupted (down system) so that the service cannot be carried out and is only done manually. Therefore, maintenance of a good network connection system must be carried out on a scheduled basis and does not result in system errors.
- b) System technical problems that arise cannot be resolved by local officers and can only be resolved by officers at the center (Directorate General of Sea Transportation Jakarta) so that it takes longer time for follow-up to solve them, therefore it must be supported by operational service administration officers and information technology (IT) technical officer related to the ship service system.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this study are as follows;

1. Inaportnet is an open and neutral electronic portal to facilitate the exchange of port service data and information quickly, safely, neutrally and easily. Inaportnet is integrated with relevant government agencies, port business entities, and logistics industry players to increase the competitiveness of the Indonesian logistics community.
2. In general, the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office has gone

well. This is relevant to aspects of standards and policy objectives; resource; inter-organizational communication; characteristics of implementing agents; attitude of the implementers; and the economic, social and political environment; as according to the Van Horn Varn Meter. Standard aspects of policy and communication in ship and goods services at Tanjung Perak Port have been going well. Likewise in terms of resources. Facilities and human resources at Tanjung Perak Port are adequate. In terms of the attitude of the implementers, the integrated service of ships and goods electronically has been going well. Likewise, customs processes, quarantine permits and immigration have been carried out with a single electronic-based service system (portnet) under the coordination of the Customs Office. This is supported by aspects of a supportive bureaucratic structure. The economic, social and political environment at the Port of Tanjung Perak also supports the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Port Authority Office.

3. Factors that support the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office is the readiness of supporting resources, both human resources and facilities at Tanjung Perak Port. Silver Surabaya.
4. While the inhibiting factors for the implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia number PM 157 of 2015 concerning inaportnet for ship and goods services at the Tanjung Perak Surabaya Main Port Authority Office consists of several obstacles, including network problems (down system) and technical problems in the operation of the innaportnet system.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad A. and M. Mashuri, "Analysis of the Queue System for Freight Carriers at the Port of Tanjung Perak Surabaya," ITS Journal of Science and Arts, vol. 5 no 1, pp. 2337-3520, 2016.
2. Kurniawan, K. Boror Seminar, B. Hascaryo Iskandar and S. Nasution, "Feasibility Study of Inaportnet and E-business Development Strategy at Makassar Port," Warta Research Transportation, vol. 27 no 5, 2015.
3. Andromeda et al: 2020 Clearance Settlement Using the Inaportnet System to Streamline Estimated Time Departure Journal of Transportation Vol. 20 No. August 2, 2020: 115–124
4. Andromeda et al: 2020 Clearance Settlement Using the Inaportnet System to Streamline Estimated Time Departure Journal of Transportation Vol. 20 No. August 2, 2020: 115–124
5. Haryotejo B., "Analysis of the Logistics Sector in the Context of Smooth Flow of Goods and Improving the Competitiveness of Regional Export Commodities," Journal of Borneo Administrator, vol. 9 no 3, 2013.
6. Sitorus B., T. I. H. Sitorus and P. Ricardianto, "Evaluation of Information System Management and Port Information Technology," Journal of Transportation and Logistics Management (JMTransLog), vol. 03 no 03, 2016.
7. Cronin, J.J., 2003. Looking back to see forward in services marketing: some ideas to consider. *Managing Service Quality*, Vol. 13 No. 5,.
8. Dunn, W. (1999). *Introduction to Public Policy Analysis*. Yogyakarta: Gajah Mada University
9. E. Irannezhad, M. Hickman and C. G. Prato, "Modeling the Efficiency of a Port Community System as an Agent-based Process. The 6th International Workshop on Agent-based Mobility, Traffic and Transportation Models," in *Methodologies and Applications (ABMTrans 2017)*, 2017.
10. Efanty and D. Charisma Febrina, *Study on the Implementation of the National Single Window System on Indonesian Fisheries Export Activities: A Case Study at the Tanjung Perak Fish Quarantine Center Surabaya*, Surabaya: Brawijaya University, 2011.
11. F. Apriliani and Wulyo, "The Indonesian Port Integration (Inaportnet) system on waiting time for pilot and waiting time for berth," *Journal of Baruna Horizon*, vol. 1 no 2, 2017.
12. Hongxiu, L., & Reima, S., 2008. Dimensions of e-service quality: an alternative model. *Second International Conference on future generation communication and networking symposia*, pp. 29-35.
13. Indrajit, Eko and Richardus D.. 2002. *Concepts of Supply Chain Management*. PT. Grasindo. Jakarta
14. K. Tri Hapsari, Suharyono and Y. Abdillah, "Implementation of the Indonesia National Single Window (INSW) System as an Effort to Promote Smooth Flow of Export and Imported Goods (Case Study on Middle Type KPPBC Customs

- Tanjung Perak Surabaya)," Journal of Business Administration (JAB) , vol. 1 no 1, 2015.
15. M. Akbar Aswin, "Implementation of Online Clearance In and Clearance Out Services Using the Inaportnet System at the Agency at Pt. Bahtera Adhiguna," Samarinda State Polytechnic, Samarinda, 2018.
 16. M. Basuki, R. B. Susanto and H. P. Herianto, "Risk Analysis of Loading and Unloading Activities as Dwelling Time Components at Ports," in National Seminar on Applied Science and Technology III, Surabaya, 2015.
 17. Niculescu M. C. and M. Minea, "Developing a single window integrated platform for multimodal transport management and logistics," Transportation Research Procedia, vol. 14, p. 1453-1462, 2016.
 18. Kadarisman M., Yuliantini and Majid S. A., "Policy Formulation of Marine Transportation System," Journal of Transportation & Logistics Management, vol. 03 no 2, 2016.
 19. Malisan, et al: 2019 Implementation of Inaportnet in One Stop Services at Tanjung Perak Port, Surabaya. Communication Research Newsletter 2019, 31 (2): 67-74
 20. Malisan, et al: 2019 Implementation of Inaportnet in One Stop Services at Tanjung Perak Port Surabaya Transportation Research News 2019, 31 (2): 67-74
 21. Moleong, Lexy J. 2007. Qualitative Research Methodology. Revised Edition. Bandung : PT Youth Rosdakarya..
 22. Rahman, Taufik. Darmawan Napitupulu. 2016. e-Service Quality Model with Meta-Ethnography Approach e-Service Quality Model Using Meta-Ethnography Approach. IPTEK-KOM, Vol. 18 No. 2, December 2016: 81-97
 23. Ridwan, Methods and Techniques for Preparing Research Proposals, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2009.
 24. Ridwan. "Margin of Appreciation for Harmonization of Indonesian Law in the Perspective of the Four Pillars of the Asean Economic Community," Journal of Legal Supremacy Research, vol. 24 no 2, 2015.
 25. S. Lutfi Anita and I. Asmadewa, "Analysis of Import Dwelling Time at Tanjung Priok Port through Application of Theory Of Constraints," Journal of Customs and Excise Perspectives, vol. 1 no 1, 2017.
 26. Suaedi, Falih Dan Wardiyanto, Bintoro (eds). 2010. Revitalization of State Administration (Bureaucracy Reform and E-Governance). Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu
 27. Sugiyono. 2017. Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods. Bandung : Alfabeta, CV.
 28. Tachjan. 2006. Implementation of Public Policy. Bandung: AIPI.
 29. Wulyo, Farida Apriliani. 2015. Indonesian Port Integration (Inaportnet) System Against Waiting Time For Pilot And Waiting Time For Berth journal.stiamak.ac.id

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